

Traces of Jainism in Medieval Northern Kodagu

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A B S T R A C T

The advent of Jainism into South India is claimed to have occurred when Acharya Bhadrabahu is said to have migrated from Magadha to Shravanabelagola along with his followers, including Chandragupta Maurya. The extent of the influence of Jainism, particularly Digambara Jainism, can be found in the Northern Kodagu Region. During the early medieval times, there was continued and enthusiastic support accorded to the Digambara Jains in Northern Kodagu. This study explores the medieval period, which could be deemed as the period when Digambara Jainism in Northern Kodagu reached its zenith.

Key Words: Monastic Orders, Patronage, Northern Kodagu.

Introduction:

Jainism is an ancient transtheistic religion. It traces its ideologies and history through the succession twenty-four Tirthankaras. According to the Digambara Jaina tradition, during the period of Chandra Gupta Maurya, a section of Jains migrated to southern India under the leadership of Acharya Bhadrabahu, and settled at Shravanabelagola. It is believed that upon the return of the followers of Bhadrabahu after 12 years of famine, they saw that the Jains who had stayed in Magadha had started to wear white clothes, which was considered as against to Jaina tenet of aparigraha by them. Thus leading to the split of Jain Sangha into two principal sects: The Digambaras (sky-clad) and the Swethambaras (White-clad).¹

The Jain Sangha was further divided into Ganas and Sanghas, and they in turn were sub-divided into Gacchas. There have been several Digambara monastic lineages among which Mula Sangha is prominent. Mula Sangha is further classified into Nandi, Sena, Simha and Deva Sanghas. A Bhattaraka heads the traditional Digambara Jain institution. Shravanabelagola Bhattaraka is the seat of Desiya Gana and Pustaka Gaccha. Kundakonda Anvaya is a sub section that follows Acharya Kundakonda, who is a distinguished Digambara Monk and Philosopher.

Kodagu Region:

Kodagu District, formerly called as Coorg, is present in Karnataka (Fig.1) (12° 25' 14.88" N, 75° 44' 22.92" E). It is present in the ranges of Western Ghats of South-Western Karnataka. The earliest mention of this region is found in Tamil Sangam Literature. The main river in Kodagu is Kaveri, and it originates at Tala Kaveri. Kodagu District has five taluks: Madikeri, Somwarapete, Virajapete, Kushalnagar and Ponnampete (Fig.2).

Jainism in Northern Kodagu Region:

Jainism was patronized by the Gangas of Talakad. They had influence over the Gangavadi 96,000 territories, which included territories in the Kodagu Region. Their influence is found in the regions of present day Virajapete Taluk in Southern Kodagu . It is notable that during the reign of Rachamalla II in 888 CE, grants were made to Sarvanandi Deva Bhatarakka, a disciple of Sivanandi Siddantha Bhattaraka, for the maintenance of Satyavakya Jinalaya at Pennekadanga.²

The Gangas were defeated by the Cholas in Gangavadi during 1004 CE, and the conquered regions were divided and given to Kongalvas and Changalvas, who became the vassals of the Cholas. Kongalvas received the Northern Kodagu Region along with parts of present day Arkalgud Taluk in Hassan District. Northern Kodagu is bordered by the Hassan District which is an important centre for Digambara Jains. Somvarapete Taluk is present in the northern region of Kodagu and is adjacent to Hassan District. Both Kongalvas and early Changalvas were Jains, and religion had a strong influence on their rule.³ Mullur, in Shanivarasante Hobli, Somwarapete Taluk was one of the main Jain centers of this region. The Jaina Basadis of Mullur indicates the patronage by Kongalvas. The monument premises consist of three Basadis namely Parshwanatha, Santhinatha and Chandranatha Basadi (Fig.3). The Basadis are relatively plain granite structures built by Kongalvas in Chola Ganga Style with a simple square plan and a Mukhamantapa. The Vimana of the Basadis are not much ornate, showcasing the primitive Dravidian Style. The Parshwanatha Basadi was built by the queen Pochchabbarasi, wife of the ruler Rajendra Chola Kongalva II. An inscription dated 1058 CE refers to grant of various villages to the Basadi⁴. The inscription found on the pedestal of Santhinatha idol refers to re-consecration of the Basadi by Mallisena Deva. This could be palaeographically assigned to the middle of the 12th Century⁵ (Fig.4). So, it might indicate renovations during the period. Guna Sena Pandita Deva was a Jain Monk, who was the disciple of Pushpasena Siddhanthadeva belonging to Dravila Gana, Nandhi Sanga and Arungalanvaya, He is said to be the guru of Pochchabbarasi. He was granted a “vasasthala” at Mullur during the rule of Rajadhiraja Kongalva II (son of Rajendra Kongalva II and Pochchabbarasi).

He caused the excavation of a well named Nagavavi ⁷ (Fig.5). Guna Sena Pandita Deva is mentioned as the guru of Hoysala King Vinayaditya. According to the Nishidi Stone set up in his memory (Fig.6), Guna Sena Pandita Deva died in 1064 CE, He is praised for his proficiency in Arhantya, the Triratnas, the Sciences of Grammars and Agamas. ⁸

Fig.3

Fig.4

Fig.5

Fig.6

In the village of Dodda Kanagal, present in the same taluk, there is a dilapidated Basadi, which also belongs to the Kongalva period. The Tirthankara idol found in these ruins was consecrated by the ruler Tribhuvanamalla Kongalva, who was the disciple of Prabhachandra Siddanthadeva, a disciple of Meghachandra Trividyadeva of Mula Sangha, Kundakondanvaya, and Pustaka Gaccha ⁹. Prabhachandra Siddanthadeva is mentioned as the Guru of Vira Kongalvadeva who caused the Satyavakya Jinalaya ¹⁰. Prabha Chandra Siddanthadeva is mentioned as the Guru of Kongalva Ruler titled Adataraditya, and

Dr.Venkatesan states that Tribhuvanamalla Kongalva might have had this title¹¹. A Nishidi Stone present in the same village mentions about the death of Prabhachandradeva who was the eldest disciple of Subhachandradeva belonging to Mula Sangha, Desiya Gana, Pustaka Gaccha, Kundakondanvaya and Ingulesvara Bali¹².

Early Changalva Rulers who ruled alongside Kongalvas were also Jains. Chikka Hanasoge, which was under the control of Changalvas, was a prominent centre for Desiya Gana, as the Acharyas of this place founded an ascetic tradition called Hanasoge Bali¹³. Changalva Rulers had their territories in the Kodagu region, and under their rule, Jain priests belonging to Hottege Gaccha claimed exclusive jurisdiction over the Jaina Basadis at Tala Kaveri¹⁴. Kivariyayya, the chief of Maduvanga Nad, kept a vow for twelve days in the Changalva Basadi and attained Salvation.¹⁵ Changalvas asserted their influence in Northern Kodagu Region at least in Mullur by the end of 13th Century.

A chief named Hariharadeva, who ruled the territories surrounding Mullur during 1390-91 CE, acknowledged the deed of the original dedication of grants made by Rajadhiraja Kongalva and his mother Pochchabbarasi. He restored the Basadis, renewed those grants and also granted the Mullur Nad to an official named Gonkaraddi Nayakka in recognition of his valor. The Mullur Basadi was given to Bahubalideva, a Jain saint who was the disciple of Vijayakirtideva of Mula Sangha, Dravila Gana, Pustaka Gaccha, and Kundakondanvaya.¹⁶ The monastic lineage of Bahubalideva points that he belongs to the order of Bhattarakas of Shravanabelagola. Three Jaina Images belonging to 12th Century were found in a Basadi at Anjanagiri. The present Anjanagiri Basadi was constructed in 1544 CE. These idols must have been in Kalkandur, a small village in Somwarapete Taluk, a Parshwanatha Basadi is said to have been built around 1380 CE, but it was renovated in 1975 and 2001. The idols found in the present structure stands as a testament to the past.¹⁸ A number of Herostones found around Ganagur, and Malambi of the same taluk have Linga Motifs, suggesting that people here started to accept Shaivism. (Fig.7, 8 & 9).

Fig. 7

Fig. 8

Fig. 9

Conclusion:

Traces of Jainism in Kodagu Region are sparse, the topography of the region makes it arduous to explore, and due to human intervention, much evidence is being neglected, mistreated, and lost. The evidences found in this region is prone to the formation of algal biofilm, leading to natural degradation. The monuments and records found in this region must be properly documented. Extensive explorations might result in finding crucial evidences that could significantly contribute to the history of Jainism in the Northern Kodagu Region.

The 2011 Census states that about 0.05% of the total population, i.e., only 250 people, follow Jainism in Kodagu Region¹⁹. Digambara Jainism reached its pinnacle in the medieval period in the Northern Kodagu Region. With the scanty information available, it could be understood that the loss of patronage and influence of Shaivism has led to the decline of Jainism in the Northern Kodagu Region.

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